

Stochastic Nature of Large-Scale Contact Printed ZnO Nanowires Based Transistors

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Printing technology holds great potential for resource-efficient development of electronic devices and circuits. However, even after decades of research, achieving uniformly responding nanowires (NWs) based printed devices is still a challenge. To date, there is no design rule that clearly guides the fabrication of NW ensemble-based field-effect transistors (FETs) and the variables that influence device-level uniformity remain unclear. The lack of fundamental understanding severely limits the large-scale and very large-scale integration (LSI and VLSI). Herein this longstanding issue is addressed with a holistic approach that starts with optimization of the synthesis of ZnO NWs, their printing, and further processing to fabricate transistors with uniform responses (e.g., on-state current, threshold voltage). Monte Carlo simulation based on statistical analysis of printed ZnO NWs is carried out to develop a probabilistic framework that can predict the large-scale performance of FETs. As a proof of concept, inverter circuits have been developed using printed ZnO NWs based FETs. This work provides a valuable toolkit to handle the stochastic nature of FETs based on printed ZnO NW ensemble, which can be used for neuromorphic integrated circuit in the future.

by conventional Si CMOS.^[1–6] This has been demonstrated through a wide variety of devices such as sensors, transistors and simple circuits based on single or ensembles of NWs.^[7–9] In particular, owing to unique electronic/optoelectronic properties, ZnO NW has been extensively investigated for photodetectors, touch sensors and emerging neuromorphic devices (e.g., synaptic transistors) along with their real-world applications.^[10–19] Despite this, no large-scale circuit has yet been realized with bottom-up grown ZnO NWs, partly because of the noticeable difficulties in attaining device-level metric homogeneity. Intuitively, using multiple NWs across the channel instead of a single NW could alleviate the device-to-device variation problem, following the long hypothesized statistical “average effect”.^[20–22] However, the underlying theory and applicability of such an effect are still unclear, especially under the constraints of adopted printing technology.

From a top-level viewpoint, most of the electronic design today is deterministic. But, the electronic building block, i.e., the Field Effect Transistor (FET) based on ensembles of printed ZnO NWs (i.e., contact printing),^[23–25] can be considered to be “probabilistic” with noticeable uncertainties during fabrication. This is because of the lack of registration and precise dimensional control of ZnO NWs, both during synthesis and device fabrication, which makes the semiconducting body vary between different transistors.^[26] In order to exploit such uncertain devices for deterministic circuit design, several fundamental questions need to be answered, including: a) What is the distribution of the important device metrics such as on-state current, threshold voltage, on–off ratio, etc, and how can they be controlled; b) what are the bottlenecks in the current manufacturing processes; c) under which scenario the “average effect” is valid. These answers will shed light on the design rules that could potentially enable large-scale and very large-scale integration (LSI and VLSI) using printed ZnO NW ensembles, particularly for novel neuromorphic circuits.

To address these longstanding questions, we have performed a systematic study investigating the effects of several important factors and optimizing the mass performance of ZnO NW-based transistors. Furthermore, a theoretical framework has been established to relate the large-scale behaviors of the FETs to the mesoscopic properties of the printed ZnO NW ensembles. Counterintuitively, the result suggests that increasing the

1. Introduction

Semiconducting NWs hold great promise for large-area, printed electronics, offering novel functionalities that cannot be attained

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Figure 1. The overall fabrication process flow of the transistor arrays based on the printed ZnO NW ensembles. a) The NW synthesis process. For Donor A, Step 1 is the deposition of Au thin film on Si substrate, followed by Step 2 the thermal dewetting to obtain Au nanoparticles and Step 3 the CVT synthesis of ZnO NWs using the Au nanoparticle as the reaction catalyst. For Donor B, Step 1 is the dispersing of Au nanoparticles, followed by Step 2 nitrogen drying and Step 3 the CVT synthesis of ZnO NWs using the Au nanoparticle as the reaction catalyst. b) The NW based device fabrication process that involves the use of contact printing method to directionally align ZnO NWs from donor to receiver substrates. The combination of different donor and receiver substrates leads to in total three groups of devices.

homogeneity of printed ZnO NW layers on certain mesoscopic parameters may hinder the overall device performance uniformity. These results help shape the future design rule of the ZnO NW-based electronics. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that clarifies the probabilistic nature of the transistors based on the contact-printed ensemble of ZnO NWs and provides insight into the future fabrication of electronics using similar materials.

2. Results and Discussion

To shed light on the device level uniformity bottleneck, we experimentally fabricated three batches of devices investigating the influence of ZnO NW diameter and ZnO NW-dielectric interface. As shown schematically in **Figure 1**, the devices were fabricated using a hybrid approach combining dry contact printing (1 to 2 in **Figure 1b**) and standard lithography (2 to 3 in **Figure 1b**). The overall process flow can be taken from our previous work^[10] The NW donor is prepared in a tube furnace using the chemical vapor transport (CVT) method with Au nanoparticles as the growth catalyst (see **Figure 1a**). The prevalent method to obtain Au nanoparticles for NW synthesis, especially for ZnO NWs, is to use particles derived from dewetted Au thin films (Donor A), as reported in several previous works (**Figure 1a**, left).^[13,27,28] SEM characterization of the dewetted Au thin film is shown in **Figure S1a** (Supporting Information), showing a wide span from tens of to hundreds of nanometres. The corresponding diameter of synthesized NWs in this group varies from ≈ 50 nm to ≈ 400 nm (**Figures S2a,b**, Supporting Information). We first evaluate in this work the NW transistor performance following this popular approach. A Si wafer with a 300 nm SiO₂ layer (Receiver A) served as the receiver substrate and 8 nm Ti and 50 nm Au were used to form the source and drain contacts. The typical transfer and output characteristics of the ZnO NW transistor fabricated using this approach (referred to as Group 1) are displayed in **Figure 2a**. The device presents a highly doped behavior with linear output

characteristics, indicating an ohmic contact. The kink behavior is attributed to the imperfection in the metal-semiconductor or semiconductor-dielectric interface, as has been widely observed in FETs based on different materials including Si, MoS₂, metal oxide, etc.^[29–32] This behavior needs to be understood and predicted for circuit level application, especially when building analog circuits. In our devices, these “kink” behaviors are reproducible in different devices, as shown in **Figure S3** (Supporting Information). When the entire transistor arrays were measured, significant device-to-device variation was observed: the on-state current ranges from several microamperes to hundred-microamperes, with a mean (μ) and standard deviation (σ) of 48.0 and 30.8 μ A, respectively (**Figure 2b**). The threshold voltage ranges from -76 to -14 V, with μ and σ being -48.7 and 14.0 V, respectively (**Figure 2c**). We examined a total of 96 transistors for Group 1. Ten of them did not function properly as they did not switch off even at a gate voltage of -80 V due to a highly degenerate semiconductor behavior. This is a direct sign of poor uniformity in the on/off ratio and similar behavior has been reported in several previous studies.^[33–35] The degenerate semiconductor behavior is a detrimental element for large-scale fabrication of NW based FETs, similar to the role of metallic CNTs in large-scale CNT based FETs — one metallic NW/nanotube bridging the source and drain electrodes can short the entire device. The diameter of NWs in this group varies from ≈ 50 to ≈ 400 nm (**Figure S2a,b**, Supporting Information). Those ZnO NW with large diameter is believed to be the origin of the degenerate semiconductor behavior, owing to the relatively lower surface depletion and higher carrier density inside the NW.^[36] As a result of above observation, these devices are not included in the statistical analysis.

To gain insight into the influence of NW diameter on the batch behavior of NW ensembles-based transistors, we investigated another group of devices (Group 2), which had the NWs synthesized using commercial Au colloids with well-defined particle diameter (80 ± 3 nm, as specified by the supplier, also see **Figure S1b**,

Figure 2. The electrical characterization of devices from Groups 1, 2, and 3. a) The typical transfer and output characteristics of devices from Group 1. The transfer curve was measured at a V_{ds} of 2 V. b) The distribution of the on-state current for the devices in Group 1. c) The distribution of the threshold voltage for the devices in Group 1. d) The typical transfer and output characteristics of devices from Group 2. The transfer curve was measured at a V_{ds} of 6 V owing to the rising Schottky contact. e) The distribution of the on-state current for the devices in Group 2. f) The distribution of the threshold voltage for the devices in Group 2. g) The typical transfer and output characteristics of devices from Group 3. The transfer curve was measured at a V_{ds} of 1 V. h) The distribution of the on-state current for the devices in Group 3. i) The distribution of the threshold voltage for the devices in Group 3. j) The diameter comparison of NWs from Donor A and Donor B. k) The band diagram showing the ZnO-NW contact using various receiver substrate. The high quality Si_3N_4 from receiver B decreases the surface state and thus decreases the band bending. l) The box-plot comparison of on-state current from three groups of devices. m) The box-plot comparison of threshold voltage from three groups of devices.

Supporting Information) as growth catalysts (donor B, see Figure 1a). The morphology control in synthesis catalysts results in grown NWs with more uniform diameter (see Figure S2c,d, Supporting Information). Except from the used NWs, all other conditions were kept the same as the Group 1. Typical performance of individual devices from Group 2 is shown in Figure 2d. It may be noted that the threshold voltage has drastically shifted to the positive side and the output characteristics show non-linearity, especially at a small gate voltage bias. This is consistent with previous theoretical and experimental reports on several types of quasi-1D systems,^[36–38] including ZnO NWs: The decrease in NW diameter leads to an increase in threshold voltage and contact resistance. This can be understood by the diameter induced change in surface depletion layer, which further influences the net carrier density in the NW core and surface barrier potential (See Figure S4, Supporting Information and corresponding discussion). The on-state current and threshold voltage were found to be $14.5 \pm 9.0 \mu\text{A}$ and $13.7 \pm 11.0 \text{ V}$ ($\mu \pm \sigma$), respectively (Figure 2e,f). In addition, no device was found to exhibit degenerate semiconductor behavior, indicating a well-depleted channel under a moderate gate voltage bias ($\approx 0 \text{ V}$). These results are in sharp contrast to the behavior of the previous batch, reflecting a noticeable improvement in the performance uniformity. However, the performance of the individual transistor degrades due to the rising Schottky barrier and contact resistance – which is in agreement with the previous theoretical study on quasi-1D transistors.^[37] A typical scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the printed NWs (see Figure S1c,d, Supporting Information) shows the NW diameter to be $58 \pm 19 \text{ nm}$. This again reveals the significant difference in printed NWs compared to group 1 (see Figure 2j). These results illustrate that the volatility in NW diameter is one of the dominant factors preventing the attainment of uniform device behavior.

With this understanding, we further examine the contribution from the NW-dielectric interface. The third group of devices employed a high-quality Si_3N_4 (70 nm) deposited on top of the previous receiver substrate (now as Receiver B in Figure 1). Except for this aspect, the fabrication was the same as in Group 2. The typical device response has been shown in Figure 2g. Compared to Group 2, the transistors from Group 3 show a band-like transport with linear output characteristics under the low bias region and a clear current saturation at the high bias region (e.g., V_{ds} of $\approx 6 \text{ V}$). This can be attributed to the high quality Si_3N_4 -ZnO NW interface, which reduces surface states, thereby reducing ZnO NW surface band bending and carrier depletion, and contributing to an Ohmic-type contact (Figure 2k). The quality of the Si_3N_4 -ZnO NW interface can be inferred by the change in hysteresis and contact resistance, as discussed in the Figures S5 and S6 (Supporting Information). All 168 fabricated bottom gated devices work similarly with a device yield of 100%; the on/off ratio of all the devices is $\approx 10^4$ or larger. Across the arrays, the on-state current and the threshold voltage were found to be $9.7 \pm 4.2 \mu\text{A}$ and $-1.8 \pm 2.0 \text{ V}$ (Figure 2h,i). To allow a direct comparison of the three groups of devices, box charts showing the 1st and 3rd quartile, median, mean and outliers outside the 1.5 Inter-Quartile Range have been plotted for both the on-state current and threshold voltage (Figure 2l,m). It is clear from the plots that the device-to-device uniformity increases drastically from Group 1 to Group 3. The threshold voltage reduction observed from Group 2 to

Group 3 is likely because of the positive fixed charge introduced by Si_3N_4 ,^[39] whereas the reduction of on-state current can be possibly attributed to the decrease of the overall gate capacitance. In addition, we would like to emphasize that there is still room for further optimization for the devices shown in Group 3. For example, by further reducing the thickness of the dielectrics, the variation of the threshold voltage can be reduced. A first investigation with a single layer dielectric of Si_3N_4 leads to a threshold voltage of $-0.17 \pm 0.55 \text{ V}$ for the case of global back-gate (dielectric of 100 nm Si_3N_4) or $0.4 \pm 1.36 \text{ V}$ for the case of local back-gate (dielectric of 50 nm Si_3N_4 , see Figure S7, Supporting Information). The benchmarking of the device level uniformity has also been discussed in the Supporting Information associated with Figure S7 (Supporting Information). This work aims to clarify the probabilistic nature of transistors based on printed NW ensembles and to provide a viable fabrication strategy to improve device-to-device uniformity. Initial circuit-level demonstration has been included in supplementary section (see Figure S8, Supporting Information for process flow) to illustrate the promise of this approach in realizing functional circuits. The individual inverter circuit behavior has been shown in Figure S9 (Supporting Information), with a gain of ≈ 40 at a V_{dd} of 6 V. The circuits will be further optimized in terms of doping for pull up/pull down matching to attain better circuit level performance (e.g., to achieve rail-to-rail operation) and improve the circuit yield (see Figure S10, Supporting Information). Owing to abundant surface states, the ZnO NWs employed here show great promise for neuromorphic applications. For example, the charge trapping and detrapping at the surface states of NWs have been used in past to emulate the biological synapses at the device level. This is the distinct advantage of ZnO NWs based devices with respect to other alternatives such as ZnO thin film. Using such FETs in the circuits may open channels for novel neuromorphic circuit applications, and we aim to explore this in our future work.

To further analyze the printed ZnO NW ensemble, we performed a large-scale SEM characterization (Figure 3a) on a control sample fabricated under the same conditions and extracted several important mesoscopic metrics, including length (L), diameter (D), density (n) and orientation (θ) of the printed NWs. To better quantify the ensembles, we defined two types of metrics, namely global parameters (i.e., to indicate inter-device situations) and local parameters (i.e., to indicate intra-device situations). By statistically analyzing the SEM images, some features have been identified in the printed ZnO NWs (see Experimental Section):

- 1), The length of printed NWs (L , a local parameter) within the device area shows a Weibull distribution instead of a Normal distribution (Figure 3b,c; Figures S11, S12, and S13, Supporting Information).
- 2), The diameter of printed NWs (D , a local parameter) within the device area can be described using Log-logistic distribution (24 out of 35 shown a p -value > 0.05 , see Figure 3d; Figures S14, S15, and S16a,b, Supporting Information).
- 3), Printed NW density (n , a global parameter) varies between devices, following a normal distribution with mean and standard deviation $0.15/\mu\text{m}^2$ and $0.02/\mu\text{m}^2$, respectively (Figure 3e; Figure S16c, Supporting Information).
- 4), The metrics of printed NWs are correlated. Some of the observed correlations are shown in Figure 3f (between n and Scl_L), Figure 3g (between Shp_L and Scl_L), and Figure 3h (between Loc_D and Scl_D). A correlation matrix was constructed to describe the

Figure 3. The SEM characterization and statistical analysis of Group 3 devices. a) The large-scale SEM analysis of 35 devices from Group 3. b) The distribution of NW length at each pixel. The curves are fitted with Weibull distribution. c) The heatmap showing the Scale factor extracted from the NW length distribution. d) The heatmap showing the Location factor extracted from the NW diameter distribution. e) The heatmap showing the NW density. f) The scatter plot showing the distributions of NW density, Scale of NW length and their correlation. g) The scatter plot showing the shape of NW length, Scale of NW length and their correlation. h) The scatter plot showing the distributions of Location of NW diameter, Scale of NW diameter and their correlation.

correlation coefficient between the parameters of interest from the contact printed NWs, including Scl_L , Shp_L , n , Loc_D and Scl_D , as shown below (see Experimental Section).

$$(1) \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.70 & -0.60 & -0.20 & 0.28 \\ 0.70 & 1 & -0.57 & -0.14 & 0.23 \\ -0.60 & -0.57 & 1 & -0.06 & -0.03 \\ -0.20 & -0.14 & -0.06 & 1 & -0.58 \\ 0.28 & 0.23 & -0.03 & -0.58 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

To probe the probabilistic nature of FETs based on contact-printed NWs, a Monte Carlo simulation has been performed. The distribution of the mesoscopic metrics of the NWs together with their correlation are assumed to be the same as what was previously extracted (see Figures S17a–c and S18, Supporting Information and Experimental Section). The simulation is first conducted to illuminate the probability of the active materials in the channel. Three types of NWs, referred to as type 1, 2 and 3 conductive path (CP), are defined as shown in Figure 4a. This enables the assessment and comparison of the contribution

Figure 4. The theoretical analysis of mass performance of FETs based on contact-printed NW ensembles. a) The illustration showing the definition of Type-1, 2 and 3 CP with the SEM image of NW FET as an example. b–d) The simulated distribution of the Type-1, Type-2, and Type-3 CPs existed in one FET. e) The ratio between Type-2 and Type-1 CPs existed in a FET. f) The ratio between Type-3 and Type-1 CPs existed in a FET. g) The simulated and experimental probability density function (PDF) of on-state current in FET based on NW ensembles. h) The simulated and experimental probability density function (PDF) of threshold voltage in FET based on NW ensembles.

from each NW across the channel and from the NW-NW junctions. Junctions formed by three or more NWs are neglected. The result indicates that on average ≈ 20 type-1 CPs can be found in a FET (Figure 4b). This closely aligns with the experimentally extracted value of ≈ 17 type-1 CPs per device (see Figure S19, Supporting Information). The simulated standard deviation to mean

ratio (σ/μ) for the type-1 CPs between different devices is $\approx 45\%$, a value close to the experimental data of $\approx 50\%$.

On the other hand, the Type-2 and Type-3 CPs exhibit a right skewed distribution (Figure 4c,d), with mean values of ≈ 40 and 57 , respectively. On average, the ratio between Type-2 and Type-1 CP in a device is ≈ 2.14 . In only a few extreme cases, this ratio

reaches 5:1 (1.6%), 10:1 (0.08%), and 20:1 (0.02%) (Figure 4e). Similarly, the average ratio between Type-3 and Type-1 CP is ≈ 2.66 , with only 0.06% showing a ratio greater than 5:1, and no devices showing ratios greater than 10:1 and 20:1 (Figure 4f). Considering the substantial junction resistance between two van der Waals contacted NWs with surface depletion (see Section S17, Supporting Information) and the comparable amount (i.e., <5:1) between the three types of CPs, it can be concluded that our devices are primarily (i.e., at least >98.4%) dominated by the individually bridged NWs rather than by NW based junctions (i.e., Type-1 rather than Type-2 or 3 CPs). If defining that a device fails without any Type-1 CP (Type 1 and Type 2 CPs) in the channel, over the 5000 simulated cases, the failure rate is $\approx 0.02\%$ (0.00%). This is the theoretical failure rate of FET based on printed NW ensembles of similar length, orientation and density.

By further integrating the analytical equations of the FET model with the Monte Carlo simulation (see Experimental Section), we can analyze the large-scale performance of the FETs based on NW ensembles. The simulated on-state current and threshold voltage can be represented using probability density function (PDF), which matches exceptionally well with the experimental distribution (Figure 2g,i) and the extracted PDF (Figure 4g,h). The small discrepancy between the experimental and theoretical PDF of on-state current can be because of several reasons: 1) inaccuracy incurred from SEM characterization and statistical analysis. Although we employed a large-scale SEM analysis to reveal the entire picture and statistical relationships, this is still not a full area study covering all the NWs in all devices. The statistics used for parameters of NWs may deviate from the real one and this could lead to the discrepancy at device level. 2) The number of transistors tested may need to reach a larger value to show a more precise PDF. Future work includes getting more statistical data to further improve the developed model. The described strategy is a general method to evaluate the batch behavior of the NW based FETs, if the mesoscopic metrics of the printed NWs are known (e.g., based on SEM characterizations) and the approximations employed in the simulation are met. We would like to highlight that the printing method we employed cannot control the exact location of each NW. However, it is possible to control the statistics of NW printing density, length, diameter, as we precisely control the NW printing and synthesis process. This lays the foundation to employ the Monte Carlo method.

The established framework also allows for a comprehensive exploration of the impact of mesoscopic parameters (e.g., NW diameter, length, density, orientation) on the overall performance of NW based FETs. This investigation will provide valuable insights into the limitations on the NW based FETs in terms of performance uniformity, and will offer the guidance on potential avenue for improvement for future LSI applications. Particularly, the developed framework allows for scrutinising two assumptions prevalent among researchers in NW electronics: (A) The enhancement of homogeneity in printed NW layers would lead to improved device uniformity; (B) Increasing the density of printed NWs contributes to a higher device uniformity (i.e., the average effect).

When the influence of NW-metal contact and NW-dielectric interface is minimized to a non-dominant level (as optimized in experiment), the performance of each FET based on NW ensembles is predominantly dictated by the diameter (D) and length

(L) of the NWs within the device area—two local parameters. Additionally, the relative positioning of each NW also plays a role, as it determines the conductive path and electrostatic screening. On a global scale, the entire transistor arrays are characterized by global parameters that define the local NW scenario within each device area. These global parameters encompass nanowire density (n), diameter distribution (Loc_D and Scl_D), and length distribution (Scl_L and Shp_L). Notably, the last four global parameters determine the values of the two local parameters (D and L), i.e., through Log-logistic and Weibull distributions, respectively.

The emergence of non-uniformity can then be classified into three distinctive sources: global parameter (inter-device) non-uniformity, reflecting the spatial variations among different devices; local parameter (intra-device) non-uniformity, determining the specific characteristics of NW bodies within the channel area of a device (it is noteworthy that identical global parameter pairs, such as Loc_D and Scl_D , may result in different local parameters, e.g., D); and, lastly, the uncontrolled coordination of NWs—an intrinsic factor originating from contact printing. From the fabrication viewpoint, the first two sources of volatilities can be mitigated through measures such as optimizing NW synthesis to attain more uniform NWs. However, the last source of volatility remains unavoidable unless there is a shift in the printing method.

To further elucidate the consequences of the improving the uniformity of the printed NWs, simulation has been carried out using the developed framework. Assuming the correlation matrix remains the same, the decrease in μ (Scl_D) (e.g., by further improving the overall diameter control of the synthesized NWs, see Figure 5a; Figures S20a,d, Supporting Information for illustrations) and σ (Scl_D) (e.g., by further decreasing the spatial inter-device difference in diameter distributions, see Figure 5b; Figure S20b,d, Supporting Information) would lead to a more uniform on-state current in the devices (Figure 5a,b). This is consistent with the presumption (A), and we therefore name the concerned mesoscopic parameters as normal parameters. Increasing the homogeneity of normal parameters of printed NW layers could lead to more uniform device behaviors. By contrast, the decrease in σ (Loc_D) (see Figure 5c; Figure S20c,e, Supporting Information) would lead to a larger variation in the on-state current (Figure 5c). Similarly, decreasing the standard deviation in NW density is also predicted to lead to more non-uniform array performance (see Figure 5d). This indicates that the increase of the uniformity in the above discussed mesoscopic metrics in turn decreases the device performance uniformity, opposite to the presumption (A). The concerned mesoscopic parameters are named as anomalous parameters. Overall, to obtain a better device level uniformity, the normal mesoscopic parameters should be minimized, and the anomalous parameters should be kept to a suitable (non-minimized) value.

Such a counterintuitive conclusion is the result of compensation enabled by the negative correlation between the mesoscopic parameters. For example, when the influence from metal-NW contact and NW-dielectric interface are not dominant, the I_{on} of a FET based on NW ensembles is largely determined by two aspects, the number of Type-1 CPs (which is then determined by Scl_L and n) and the corresponding NW diameters. With the above observed correlation matrix, these two aspects are

Figure 5. The prediction of the uniformity of FET arrays affected by the mesoscopic metrics of contact-printed NW ensembles. a) The illustration showing the change of the mean value in scale of NW diameter, ScI_D , and how this influences the group behavior of FETs. b) The illustration showing the change of the standard deviation in scale of NW diameter, ScI_D , and how this influences the group behavior of FETs. The results in (a) and (b) show that decrease of variation lead to an increased uniformity in on-state current. c) The illustration showing the change of the standard deviation in location of NW diameter, Loc_D , and how this influences the group behavior of FETs. d) The illustration showing the change of the standard deviation in NW density, n , and how this influences the group behavior of FETs. The results in (c) and (d) show that decrease of variation does not lead to an increased uniformity in on-state current. e) The simulated result showing how the uniformity of on-state current will be affected by the increase of mean NW density, n . The correlation and parameters are all extracted from experimental data. The trend is consistent with the “average effect”. f) The simulated result showing how the uniformity of on-state current will be affected by the increase of average NW density, n , using a hypothetical correlation defined in method. The result is inconsistent with the “average effect”, showing a counter example.

negatively correlated. A large variation in both aspects does not necessarily lead to a non-uniform on-state current between devices — the device with NWs of larger diameter but fewer Type-1 CPs can be similar to the device with NWs of smaller diameter but more Type-1 CPs. In other words, the variation in both parameters could cancel the adverse impact of each other. Instead, decreasing the spatial variation in one of the two parameters would result in a rising variation in I_{on} , as the compensation effect decreases, and the variation contributed from the other parameters starts to play a stronger role.

Similarly, we found that the validity of presumption (B) also depends on the correlation matrix. For example, with the existing matrix, increase in the NW density (n) would lead to a more uniform on-state current, along with more Type-1 CPs (Figure 5e). This is consistent with the popularly believed average effect. However, if a more prominent negative correlation between n and Loc_D were employed (i.e., -0.5), the I_{on} starts to show a non-monotonic dependency with the increase of n , despite of the monotonic increase of Type-1 CPs (See Figure 5f; Figure S21, Supporting Information). This is in sharp contrast to the known “average effect”. Therefore, the correlation relationship between various mesoscopic parameters of NWs is critical to the large-scale performance of FETs and this calls for a holistic material-to-device co-design for large-scale electronics based on contact-printed NWs or similar nanostructures.

3. Conclusion

To summarize, we have presented a systematic study on the FETs based on contact-printed ZnO NW ensembles and revealed the probabilistic nature of their performance variations that arise from the varying semiconducting body. A theoretical framework that describes the mass behavior of the FETs have been developed and a viable fabrication strategy toward large-scale uniform transistor arrays have been identified. The design rule of FETs based on contact printed ZnO NWs or similar NW materials has been suggested. We believe, this work lays a strong foundation for the future realization of LSI and VLSI novel neuromorphic circuits based on printed NWs.

4. Experimental Section

The ZnO NW Growth: The ZnO NW was grown following CVT method in a tube furnace. A mixture of Carbon (0.5 g) and Graphite (0.5 g) powder was used as the source. For NWs used in Group 1, 3 nm Au thin film was deposited by electron-beam evaporation and dewetted at 1050 °C. The synthesis was carried out at 950 °C with an Ar of 1000 sccm as the carrier gas. For NWs used in Groups 2, 3, and 4 (Supporting Information), the commercial Au colloids with defined diameter (80 or 50 nm) were used as the synthesis catalyst. The reaction was carried out at 880 °C for 2 h with an Ar of ≈ 2000 sccm as the carrier gas. Detailed synthesis procedure can be found in ref. [10].

The NW Printing: A closed loop controlled, automated contact printing setup has been employed to carry out the NW printing process. The dry printing of NWs is advantageous in the bottom gated FET scenario because it preserves the intrinsic nanowire-bottom gate dielectric interface, and the device configuration is beneficial for neuromorphic applications. The details of NW printing can be found in ref. [25].

The Device Fabrication: After the printing of NWs, the samples were heated at ≈ 160 °C for 5 min to increase the adhesion between NWs and the underlying substrate. Lithography, electron-beam evaporation and lift-off were used to define the source and drain electrodes of NW based FETs. It should be noted that the NW baking and lift-off process were carefully controlled in order to remove the unwanted NWs between neighboring devices.^[10] For NW FET with local gate control, an ultra-clean, buried gate strategy were employed. Without it, the NWs can hardly be printed onto the location of interest. This will be explained in our future work.

Monte Carlo Simulation: The Monte Carlo simulation was carried out by a MATLAB code. The printed NWs were assumed to be in the shape of cylinders with a density (n). The length and diameter of NWs within each device were assumed to follow the Weibull (Scl_L and Shp_L) and Log-logistic (Loc_D and Scl_D) distributions, as confirmed by the experiment. All these parameters (Scl_L , Shp_L , n , Loc_D and Scl_D) vary spatially following the normal distribution (marginal univariate distributions), consistent with the experimental data. The correlation matrix between Scl_L , Shp_L , n , Loc_D and Scl_D was extracted from the large-scale SEM analysis. Cholesky decomposition was employed to create a multivariate dataset (i.e., 5 dimensions) with the same correlation and marginal univariate distributions. The orientation θ of the NW was assumed to follow a circular normal distribution plus a modification term, $\pi \cdot$ Bernoulli (0.5), which was in reasonable agreement with the statistical analysis from the SEM characterizations (see Figure S18a,b, Supporting Information and Experimental Section). No spatial variation in orientation was considered here for simplicity. The channel length and width in the simulation were set to 11.5 and 220 μm respectively, the same as the experiment. In this way, it can reconstruct a model that well agrees with the printed NW ensembles obtained in the experiment and investigate their statistical patterns.

The relationship between average carrier mobility μ and NW radius r was assumed to be $\mu = 0.87r + 4.36$. This leads to an average mobility ranging from 20 to 50 cm^2/Vs , which agrees with previous results in ZnO NW FET study from other groups,^[13,40] and our own work.^[41] The threshold voltage V_{th} and radius r were assumed to follow the equation $V_{th} = 5.0r/4.4$. The slope used in this equation was extracted from two batches of FETs with NWs of different mean diameter. One batch of NWs was synthesized using 80 nm Au colloids and the other batch was synthesized using 50 nm Au colloids. This leads to the mean NW diameter of ≈ 60 nm and ≈ 45 nm, respectively.

For the electrical part, classical FET equations were used to describe the electrical behavior. Considering the case of FET based on a single NW, the channel current I_D in the linear region satisfies the following equation, if the contribution of the contact resistance was neglected:

$$I_{D,i} = \frac{\mu_i C_{ox,i}}{L_i^2} \left(V_G - V_{T,i} - \frac{V_{DS}}{2} \right) V_{DS} \quad (2)$$

where V_{DS} , V_G , V_T , denote the drain to source bias, gate voltage and threshold voltage, respectively. L and μ represent the channel length and average field-effect mobility, respectively. C_{ox} is the gate capacitance of the single NW based device and depends on the diameter and length of the NW. Considering the conclusion drawn from 1 that more than 98.4% of the devices were dominated by Type-1 CP, the behavior of FET based on NW ensembles can be approximately regarded as the summation of contributions from each Type-1 CP, i.e.,

$$I_{on} \approx \sum I_{D,i} \quad (3)$$

For C_{ox} , COMSOL simulation was employed to estimate its value for each NW (see Figure S22a-f, Supporting Information and the discussion on the screening effect for multi-NW case). Furthermore, based on previous reports on NW based FETs, several reasonable assumptions have been made to allow us to carry out further investigations:

i), the field-effect mobility of single NW based FETs follows a linear relationship with its diameter^[38]; ii), the threshold voltage of single NW based FET was negatively correlated with its diameter.^[36] This phenomenon has also been confirmed in our own studies. The Monte Carlo simulation was executed for 5000 cycles, representing device arrays of 5000 devices.

To study the influence of mesoscopic parameters of printed NWs, random number generator in MATLAB was controlled to enable valid comparisons. The correlation matrix used in Figure 5f is,

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.70 & -0.60 & -0.20 & 0.28 \\ 0.70 & 1 & -0.57 & -0.14 & 0.23 \\ -0.60 & -0.57 & 1 & -0.5 & -0.03 \\ -0.20 & -0.14 & -0.5 & 1 & -0.58 \\ 0.28 & 0.23 & -0.03 & -0.58 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In addition, the value of standard deviation of *Loc_D* was set to be 1 nm, instead of the value of 0.07 nm extracted from the experiment. These two changes were applied to the simulation for Figure 5f only to illustrate the counterexample of the average effect.

Finite Element Simulation: COMSOL Multiphysics 5.2a was used to simulate the gate capacitance of NW based FET.

SEM Analysis: The SEM analysis was performed using imageJ.

Statistical Analysis: The statistical analysis was performed using Minitab 19.

The length of printed NWs (*L*, a local parameter) within the device area shows a Weibull distribution instead of a Normal distribution (Figure 3b). Of the 35 devices analyzed, 29 passed the hypothesis test with a *p*-value over 0.05 (see Figure S11, Supporting Information). This observation may be related to the previously reported NW fracture process governed by the Weibull weakest point probability theory,^[42,43] but further studies were needed. In this work, the scale (*ScL*) and shape (*ShpL*) values were extracted from the Weibull distribution and plot them spatially to represent the global scenario (see Figure 3c; Figure S12, Supporting Information). Both *ScL* and *ShpL* vary spatially (global parameters) and were normally distributed (*p* > 0.05), as shown in Figure S13 (Supporting Information).

The diameter of printed NWs (*D*, a local parameter) within the device area can be described using Log-logistic distribution (24 out of 35 showed a *p*-value > 0.05, see Figure S14, Supporting Information), instead of Normal distribution (only 5 out of 35 passed the normality test). Similarly, the extracted location (*LocD*, which predominantly determines the mean value, a global parameter) and scale (*ScD*, which predominantly determines the standard deviation, a global parameter) have been shown in the heatmap (Figure 3d; Figure S15, Supporting Information) and they were both normally distributed (*p* > 0.05, Figure S16a,b, Supporting Information).

The mesoscopic parameters of contact printed NWs were found to correlate with each other noticeably. The correlation was the result of multiple factors including NW synthesis and NW printing. For example, this study have identified that *n* is negatively correlated with *ScL* with a correlation coefficient *r* of -0.6 (Figure 3f). This can be understood under the assumption that the printing yield was proportional to the free area available on the receiver substrate. At a given printing pressure, longer NWs (if their diameters were similar) would occupy a larger area on the receiver substrate, reducing the subsequent printing yield and ultimately leading to a lower overall NW density when compared to the case with shorter NWs. Similarly, different levels of correlations were observed for different combinations of two parameters of interest. Here it aim to develop a data-driven method to empirically describe the complex relationship in metrics of contact printed ZnO NWs with some level of physics understanding; a pure physics-based model was also important but is outside the focus of this paper.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

large-area electronics, Monte Carlo simulation, printed electronics, statistics, ZnO nanowire

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